

Operational Storage: Think short and long term

Store & Manage

Secure Active Data

Every stage of the data lifecycle centers around data storage. Proper storage maintenance throughout the lifecycle is imperative to ensure data remains secure and adheres to recommended safety protocols.

- **Data Safety:** Protect the welfare of research participants and confirm the integrity of research data. Harvard's [Data Safety system](#) supports the submission, review, and management of data use.
- **Data Security:** Ensure confidential and sensitive data is maintained. Harvard maintains five Data Security Levels. Review the [Research Data Security Levels with Examples](#) to determine your risk level.
- **Software:** Protect your software systems using strategies like anti-virus software, updating applications and OS, firewall, and anti-intrusion software. Digital access should be limited to those that need it.
- **Hardware:** Ensure appropriate security controls for the physical location(s) where your computers, servers, and data storage reside. Physical access should be restricted to those that need access.

Determine Appropriate Data Storage Locations

Review institutional storage options to better understand where to store data based on behavior, performance, and means of access. The type of data you are working with, or the Data Security Level, will dictate where and how that data needs to be stored or handled.

- **Harvard University Collaborative Matrix:** Aligns Harvard's Data Security Levels with storage platforms
- **HMS IT Research Data Storage Offerings:** HMS offers three primary storage types with distinct behaviors, performance, and means of access
- **FAS Data Storage Offerings:** FASRC offers three different software applications with variety of performance characteristics

Create a Data Backup Plan

Having at least one backup can help prevent data mishaps. Harvard systems automatically provide secure backup in geographically distributed locations.

- **CrashPlan (Code42):** Ensures critical data is recoverable in the event of a loss or compromise or data. [CrashPlan is available to HMS and HSDM](#) quad-based personnel for free. [CrashPlan is also available for FAS departments, Central Administration, and other schools](#) through Harvard University IT (HUIT).
 - Backs up continually over almost any network on or off-campus

Harvard Research Data Management Lifecycle Checklist

- Recovers documents from any computer via a web browser
- Stores document copies for a minimum of 60 days

Research data that is temporarily not in Harvard systems benefits from following the 3-2-1 Rule.

- **3-2-1 Rule:** General fail-proof backup strategy:
 - Three copies of the data (e.g., original + external/local + external/remote)
 - Two types of storage formats (e.g., external hard drive + cloud location)
 - One storage type is offsite (e.g. geographically distributed location)

Resolve Access Permissions

Ensure data is always shared with the PI and always resides in a shared location with more than one owner to help support the longevity and sustainability of research. Individual data should be moved to a shared location prior to completion of a project or departure from a lab. Access permissions also apply to a variety of storage locations including Electronic Lab Notebooks and website content.

★ **Utilize the [RDM Offboarding Checklist](#) to offboard employees or team members from the lab or project**
When employees leave, they take their skills and institutional knowledge with them. It is important to record essential informative information related to projects and datasets to ensure the success of future users. Use the [RDM Offboarding Checklist](#) and [Knowledge Transfer File Template](#) to guide the knowledge transfer process.